

An exploratory framework of land-sea movement model for early Austronesian migration

Luo Hongpeng¹, He Jie^{*2}

¹ Tianjin University – Tianjin, China

² Harbin Institute of Technology, Shenzhen – Shenzhen, China

*Corresponding author

Correspondence: hejie2021@hit.edu.cn

ABSTRACT

Archaeological, linguistic, and genetic evidence confirms that the Austronesian language family originated on the Southeast Asian mainland. However, these interdisciplinary findings remain inadequately integrated within a unified geospatial framework, leading to fragmented research efforts and potential oversight of critical insights due to insufficient digital integration. This study investigates human spatial mobility patterns across terrestrial and maritime environments, contextualized within the Austronesian expansion from the Yangtze River Delta, a region associated with early rice cultivation (pre-domestication), to continental Southeast Asia and the broader Pacific. Methodologically, the paper developed an exploratory analytical framework using Geographic Information Systems (GIS) tools to simulate least-cost corridors and optimal migration pathways. The framework yields four archaeologically interpretable dimensions: (1) land-sea mobility contrasts, (2) seasonal movement variability, (3) round-trip journey dynamics, and (4) comparative analyses of least-cost versus alternative migration strategies. By bridging environmental and anthropogenic factors, this framework advances understanding of early human migration patterns, provides a foundation for analyzing cultural identity through spatial behavior, and establishes a baseline for developing refined maritime mobility models.

Keywords: the Austronesians, Maritime Movement, GIS, Least Cost Corridor, Optimal Path

Introduction

Understanding maritime mobility provides a critical lens for deciphering the relationship between humans and their environment. The linguistic and archaeological records of the Austronesian populations distributed across islands spanning the Indo-Pacific archipelago demonstrate the unique patterns of long-distance maritime dispersal. Archaeologist P. Bellwood has theorized that oceans functioned not as barriers but as conduits for resource accessibility and rapid expansion (the "Express Train" model, P. Bellwood 1979). This study constructs an analytical framework for land-sea mobility patterns within the dual contexts of the Austronesian continental and maritime expansion to elucidate the spatial differentiation of early human migration routes.

The Austronesians

The Austronesian language family constitutes the most extensive prehistoric human agricultural expansion (Diamond and Bellwood 2003) and ranks as the world's largest language family by geographical distribution, comprising over 1,200 languages (Tryon and Tryon 2011). A landmark 2020 genomic study employing ancient DNA evidence confirmed that southern mainland Chinese populations dating back over 8,000 years represent the ancestral source of this language family (Yang et al. 2020).

In this study, specific terminological conventions are applied to ensure conceptual precision: *The Austronesians / The Austronesian Populations / Early Austronesians*: Refers exclusively to the ancestral Proto-Austronesian-speaking populations and their descendant ethnolinguistic groups who undertook the historical dispersal. This term emphasizes the agency of human migration. *The Austronesian Language Family*: Denotes the linguistic phylum comprising more than 1,200 descendant languages across its ten primary branches.

Maritime Movement Simulation Potential

Maritime simulation methodologies offer significant potential for reconstructing historical seafaring behaviors and environmental interactions. Early documentation of Polynesian celestial navigation emerged in *The Raft Book* (Gatty 1999 [1943]). Between 1964 and 1968, David Lewis successfully replicated a 1,400 km ancient voyage using traditional navigation techniques relying on celestial observations, biological indicators, and historical documents (Lewis 1964; 1966; 1972). Contemporary computational approaches enable sophisticated simulations through tools like Alberti's ArcGIS-Python integrated toolbox, which generates least-cost sailing paths (LCPs) while visualizing real-time wind patterns and maritime rhythms (Alberti 2018; Perttola 2022). Recent advancements incorporate seasonal winds and archaeological parameters to create dynamic seascape models (Gheorghide and Spencer 2024).

Research Questions

Bellwood's foundational hypothesis (1985) posits southeastern Asian origins for the Austronesian populations, particularly from early Chinese agricultural centers, followed by maritime diversification through island archipelagos (Bellwood et al. 1995; Bellwood 2007; 2017). Subsequent linguistic analyses have refined our understanding of mainland-based linguistic diffusion (Deng and Wang 2003; 2007; Guo, Deng, and Wang 2023). Archaeological evidence demonstrates that rice-cultivating populations from the Yangtze Delta migrated along coastal routes, interacting with hunter-gatherer communities rather than directly colonizing islands (Higham 2019). Genomic studies corroborate both agricultural origins (Yang et al. 2020) and coastal migration patterns (Wei et al. 2017).

Multidisciplinary evidence regarding the Austronesian populations warrants systematic spatial integration to enhance cultural interpretation. While GIS-based spatial analyses have been extensively implemented in Mediterranean maritime studies (Leidwanger 2013; Safadi 2016; Alberti 2018; Bilotti, Kempf, and Morillo Leon 2024), comparable research in the Western Pacific remains underdeveloped (Perttola 2022). Currently, the Austronesian scholarship predominantly

83 relies on discrete archaeological, linguistic, and genetic datasets. This disciplinary fragmentation
84 is exacerbated by two critical limitations: (1) the scarcity of culturally relevant spatial data compared
85 to Mediterranean trade records, and (2) inadequate foundational models for simulating Pacific
86 maritime navigation routes.

87 This study proposes an exploratory land-sea movement model addressing three research
88 priorities constrained to Southeast Asia's coastal transition zones:

- 89 1. What methodological adaptations are required for applying this framework to the
90 Austronesians archaeological sites?
- 91 2. How effectively does the model represent land-sea spatial continuities?
- 92 3. To what extent can the framework synthesize archaeological, linguistic, and genetic
93 evidence while enabling cultural inferences?

94 **Exploratory Framework of the Land-Sea Movement Model**

95 The proposed model's novelty stems from its dual analysis of terrestrial/maritime mobility
96 patterns and systematic integration of land-sea spatial continuities.

97 **Study Area and Geospatial Parameters**

98 The scope of research for this exploratory framework (Figure 1) considers two directions: the
99 continental diffusion and maritime diffusion of early Austronesians. The starting point is the lower
100 reaches of the Yangtze River region, which served as the zone of initial rice cultivation (pre-
101 domestication), according to Bellwood (2024). Selected area in this research intuitively reflect the
102 differentiation between continental and maritime diffusion undertaken by early Austronesians. The
103 direction of continental diffusion involves areas along the southeastern coast of Asia, such as
104 Vietnam (Higham 2019), while maritime diffusion includes regions like Philippines (Bellwood 2017).

105 When running path simulation analyses in computer software, a clear start and end point are
106 often required as input data (ESRI 2025d). Archaeological sites with explicit spatial coordinates
107 have been discovered, so this exploratory framework will use these site points as the starting and
108 ending regions for the dispersal of early Austronesians. It is important to note that the movement
109 patterns of early human origin and dispersal are evidently not a simple point-to-point model.
110 Human movements are generally more complex (Wheatley and Gillings 2002; van Leusen 2002).
111 Include Liangzhu, Liang Island, Kequtou, Fugutun site, Dafenkeng site, Fengbitou site, Shenwan
112 site, Man Bac site, An Son site, and Andarayan site (Bellwood 2017) (Figure 1). It should be noted
113 that the selected site points represent a region. For example, the Liangzhu site represents the
114 departure of early Austronesians from the lower Yangtze River region, rather than indicating that
115 early Austronesians started their dispersal from the Liangzhu site itself. These site points should
116 be sufficiently sparse yet not overly dispersed.

117 Beyond origin-destination parameters, the navigational environment constitutes a critical
118 geospatial component, synthesized primarily from terrestrial and marine geodatasets.

119 *Land Data*

120 The terrestrial data employs 90 m-resolution Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) Digital
121 Elevation Models (DEM) obtained from the Geospatial Data Cloud platform
122 (<http://www.gscloud.cn>). The high-resolution SRTM DEM was generalized to create a smoothed
123 topographic surface suitable for large-scale modeling. This was achieved through resampling to a
124 10 km resolution, which effectively reduces localized noise and interpolation artifacts that are
125 disproportionate at our intended scale of analysis (Hengl 2006; Gillings, Hacıgüzeller, and Lock
126 2020; Gheorghide and Spencer 2024). While this process sacrifices fine-scale accuracy, it
127 ensures that the topographic parameters, such as slope, aspect, hillshade, are representative at
128 the scale of our model units. Derived topographic parameters include: *Slope* (vertical mobility
129 constraints), *Aspect* (horizontal movement vectors), and *Hillshade* (visualizations).

130 The dispersal of the Austronesian populations is believed to have occurred approximately
131 5,500 years ago (Bellwood 2017). While modern DEM reflect post-2000 terrain conditions from

132 STS Endeavour surveys, their application remains justified given the methodological challenges
 133 of paleotopographic reconstruction. Human activities and hydrological erosion altered the
 134 topography, especially in the lower Yangtze River (Liu et al. 2021). The effectiveness of erosion
 135 and hydrological models remains contentious (Mehrer 2005). The pragmatic approach within this
 136 exploratory framework balances model validity with data availability.

137

138 **Figure 1** – Study area, and continental and maritime diffusion of early Austronesians
 139 on the southeastern coast of Asia (base map provided by ArcGIS Pro)

140 **Sea Data**

141 Maritime mobility modeling necessitates alternative approaches to terrestrial elevation analysis
 142 due to the inapplicability of DEM in oceanic contexts. Seasonal dynamics and temporal variations
 143 constitute critical parameters, particularly through their manifestation in monsoonal wind regimes.
 144 Historical navigation practices demonstrate that mariners derived velocity estimates and
 145 directional bearings through celestial observations, including stellar positioning and solar azimuth
 146 calculations (Gatty 1999; Gooley 2017). Sea simulations must further integrate three anisotropic
 147 factors: atmospheric wind patterns (direction/speed), ocean current dynamics (vector/velocity),
 148 and vessel navigational constraints (kinematic parameters) (Leidwanger 2013; Safadi 2016; Gal,
 149 Saaroni, and Cvikel 2023; Gheorghide and Spencer 2024).

150 This framework model employs $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ resolution wind data, and consists of publicly
 151 available u and v vector data. The spatial resolution of approximately 28 kilometers at equatorial
 152 latitudes balances regional-scale analysis with computational feasibility, while u/v component
 153 selections prioritize wind direction as the primary modeling variable over auxiliary nautical factors.
 154 Utilizing January and August 2000 datasets to represent northeast winter (November to March)
 155 and southwest summer (April to September) monsoonal conditions respective (Pertola 2022).
 156 The data from the Asia-Pacific Data Research Center (<http://apdrc.soest.hawaii.edu/las86>), part
 157 by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA).

158 **Methodology and Framework**

159 *Model Parameters*

160 GIS integrate computer and database technologies to systematically process, analyze, and
161 visualize spatial data (Mehrer 2005). These scalable platforms enable geospatial projection of both
162 spatial and non-spatial variables (Alberti 2018), forming the foundation for contemporary maritime
163 mobility simulations. Currently, most ocean mobility models have been developed using GIS-
164 based tools, such as polygon-based modeling (Harpster and Chapman 2019) and social network
165 analysis models (SNA) (Trapero Fernández and Aragón 2022). In this exploratory framework, the
166 tool of *Distance Accumulation* (ESRI 2025e) in ArcGIS Pro 3.4.2 was utilized, followed by the *Least*
167 *Cost Corridor* (ESRI 2025g) and *Optimal Path as Line* (ESRI 2025h), then the cumulative cost
168 corridors and paths were constructed (Indruszewski and Barton 2008; Gustas and Supernant
169 2017a; 2017b; 2019; Moutsiou and Agapiou 2019; Verhagen, Nuninger, and Groenhuijzen 2019).
170 It is important to note that human activities are complex (Wheatley and Gillings 2002; van Leusen
171 2002). Although computational results are more easily observed as "paths", actual human diffusion
172 is more likely to occur in *Areas / Corridor* rather than along *Lines / Paths*, necessitating critical
173 interpretation of model outputs.

174 The calculation of resistance and attraction constitutes the critical factor in the model framework.
175 Cost parameters include isotropic and anisotropic components (Indruszewski and Barton 2008;
176 He 2008). *Isotropic* costs refer to movement costs unaffected by directional variations, such as
177 forests, meadows, and other land cover types. *Anisotropic* costs describe movement energy
178 consumption influenced by directional changes, such as wind patterns, wave dynamics, and solar
179 elevation angles (ESRI 2025a; 2025f). Land and ocean movement models are primarily governed
180 by anisotropic factors, such as the influence of slope and wind from different directions.

181 In this framework model, the first step involves calculating the cumulative cost using the
182 Distance Accumulation Tool (ESRI 2025g; 2025h). For the land movement model, the Input
183 Surface Raster and Input Cost Raster both utilize the DEM, whereas the Input Vertical Raster uses
184 slope data. The vertical factor (VF) follows a symmetric inverse linear relationship (Figure 2) (ESRI
185 2025c), with the vertical relative moving angle (VRMA) constrained between -55° and 50° (Llobera
186 2000; He 2008). The Input Horizontal Raster incorporates aspect data, and the horizontal factor
187 (HF) is modeled as a linear function (Figure 2) (ESRI 2025b).

188 In the sea movement model, the Input Surface Raster is assigned a constant value of 1 to avoid
189 calculation issues with value of zero are invalid and the NoData value is treated as a barrier in
190 ArcGIS Pro (ESRI 2025e), while the Input *Cost Raster* incorporates wind speed data. The *Input*
191 *Horizontal Raster* utilizes wind direction data, with the HF as a linear function. This configuration
192 results in maximum resistance when the horizontal relative moving angle (HRMA) approaches -
193 180° , indicating movement directly opposing wind direction (ESRI 2025b).

194

195 **Figure 2** – Symmetric inverse linear vertical factor graph (Left) and linear horizontal
196 factor graph (Right) of ArcGIS Pro 3.4 Distance Accumulation Tool (source: ESRI
197 2025b; 2025c)

198 *Framework of Land-Sea Movement Model*

199 This exploratory framework constructs a mobility simulation model based on the continental
200 and marine diffusion background of early Austronesians (Figure 3). *Land Movement Model: the*
201 *foundational dataset is DEM. To isolate terrestrial movement cost calculations, oceanic raster*
202 *values are assigned as NoData. Starting points correspond to archaeological sites linked to early*
203 *human continental expansion (Bellwood 2024). Slope and aspect function are used as vertical and*
204 *horizontal cost parameters, respectively. Sea Movement Model: core datasets integrate wind*
205 *speed and wind direction. Using ArcGIS Pro tools (ESRI 2025g; 2025h), the model generates*
206 *least-cost corridors and optimal paths. Subsequent analyses will differentiate:*

- 207 1. Terrestrial and marine movement patterns,
- 208 2. Seasonal variations (summer and winter),
- 209 3. Round-trip route feasibility,
- 210 4. Distinctions between least-cost and optimized areas.

211 These analyses aim to identify high-probability regions or corridors traversed during the
212 Austronesians expansion, with detailed discussions provided in later sections.

213 The exploratory framework uses foundational datasets as its structural baseline (orange box,
214 Figure 3). Its advanced iteration (blue box, Figure 3) incorporates a suite of enhancements to
215 achieve a more nuanced analysis. For terrestrial cost calculations, these enhancements include
216 expanded horizontal and vertical parameters such as paleo-land cover, topography derived from
217 higher-resolution DEM (He 2008), resource accessibility thresholds, technological development
218 stages, and sociocultural contexts. For marine cost calculations, the enhancements integrate
219 parameters that capture oceanic current dynamics (Safadi 2016), vessel windward performance
220 (Pertola 2022; Safadi 2016; Gal, Saaroni, and Cvikel 2023), island visibility buffers (Lewis 1964),
221 astronomically guided navigation angles (Lewis 1966; Gatty 1999), biogeographical indicators of
222 maritime zones (Gooley 2017), and cultural navigational decisions (Lewis 1972, p. 206).

223 By integrating these additional factors, the model will achieve a more comprehensive and
224 realistic simulation of the mobility patterns of early Austronesians, thereby enhancing the accuracy
225 and reliability of the diffusion scenarios presented.

226 **Results and Differentiated Analysis**

227 This exploratory framework yields four archaeological insights.

228 First, the framework conducts a comparative analysis of continental and marine diffusion.
229 Assuming that the initial continental expansion of early Austronesians proceeded sequentially, we
230 propose that they would first reach one location before moving to the next (Figure 4a) (Bradshaw
231 et al. 2019). Furthermore, we can hypothesize that once this expansion stabilizes and populations,
232 resources, and technologies have accumulated to a certain extent (Ruxton and Wilkinson 2012;
233 Gauthier 2019; Ihara et al. 2020), the diffusion may also occur simultaneously from a single point
234 to all other locations (Figure 4b).

235 Second, seasonal mobility variations are primarily reflected in marine diffusion, with the primary
236 influencing factor being changes in monsoon patterns. We can infer that the farther offshore and
237 the longer the voyage, the more pronounced the route changes due to differing monsoon
238 influences (Figures 5a, 5d, 5e, 5f), whereas short-distance voyages exhibit minimal route
239 variations (Figures 5b, 5c). However, some maritime areas and inlets experience complex local
240 wind environment changes (Gustas and Supernant 2017b; 2019), suggesting that seasonal route
241 variations may exhibit significant differences between micro-scale and macro-scale movement
242 models.

243 Third, due to the directional nature of winds and waves in the marine environment, even
244 voyages conducted within the same season may follow different routes in roundtrip. For example,
245 during winter, voyages from Fengpitou to ManBac and the return trip follow very similar routes. In
246 contrast, during summer, the voyage from Fengpitou to ManBac follows a route closer to the
247 mainland, whereas the return trip requires a longer detour (Figure 6c).

248 Fourth, in addition to the visualization of optimal paths and least cost corridors, this model
249 allows us to observe other potential transit regions. For instance, in the continental diffusion from

250 Liangzhu to Anson, although the optimal path points toward coastal areas, we can still observe
 251 possible low-cost movement directions away from the coast (Figure 7a). Similarly, during the
 252 marine movement from Fengpitou to ManBac, there appear to be additional landing opportunities
 253 (Figure 7b). Next, with more archaeological evidence, it may be possible to investigate whether
 254 the cultural remains at these landing sites are associated with the entire maritime route.

255

256 **Figure 3 – Exploratory Framework of Land-Sea Movement Model.**

257 In conclusion, this exploratory framework of land-sea movement model, based solely on
 258 environmental factors, contributes by identifying regions that early Austronesians were more likely
 259 to reach or traverse during expansions. It is important to recognize that human behavior is
 260 influenced by a multitude of factors (Puleston and Winterhalder 2019), and even the remarkable
 261 willpower of individuals often involves contending with nature in extreme environments (Lewis
 262 1974). Therefore, the model's simulation results should be further interpreted in conjunction with
 263 historical, cultural, and archaeological evidence (Shennan and Sear 2021).

(a)

(b)

264

265

266

267

Figure 4 – Terrestrial and maritime diffusion (a) occur sequentially from Liangzhu to Kequtou, ShamWan, ManBac, AnSon, and (b) take place simultaneously from Liangzhu to other sites.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

268

269

270

Figure 5 – Seasonal paths from Liangzhu to (a) Andarayan, (b) Dabenkeng, (c) Fengpitou, (d) ShamWan, (e) ManBac, (f) Anson.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

271

272

273

Figure 6 – Roundtrip paths in different seasons from (a) Liangzhu to Andarayan, (b) Liangzhu to AnSon, (c) Fengpitou to ManBac, (d) Fengpitou to Andarayan.

274

275

276

277

278

Figure 7 – (a) The optimal path and cost corridors in terrestrial diffusion. It also reveals the potential low-cost directions. (b) The optimal paths and cost corridors in maritime diffusion, it also identifies potential dispersion pathways, such as routes around islands, and possible landing zones.

279

Discussion

280

281

282

283

284

285

286

287

288

289

290

291

292

293

294

295

296

Returning to the first research question, how can this exploratory framework of the land-sea movement model be applied to archaeological sites? This framework used wind data as an initial attempt, which is still preliminary, but operational. Through the experience of building least-cost models, we understand that the rational organization of resistance and attraction factors is key to successfully constructing a complete and effective model (Di Piazza 2014; Gustas and Supernant 2017b; Dickson et al. 2019; Gustas and Supernant 2019; Safadi and Sturt 2019; McLean and Rubio-Campillo 2022). Simulating oceanic movement requires a comprehensive consideration of wind, waves, and ship conditions, which directly affect navigation (Perttola 2022) especially for peoples, such as the Austronesians, who used sailboats (Bellwood 1979; Bellwood et al. 1995). The type of ship influences its ability to sail against the wind, which can determine the wind angles at which the ship can navigate, thereby determining how it reaches its destination (Alberti 2018; Whitewright 2011; Perttola 2022). Sea waves and tides are closely related to time, and their impact is concentrated in nearshore areas, Safadi mentioned that not the entire island has suitable docking points for landings, and waves, geomorphology directly influence the selection of landing points (Safadi 2016). The next step of framework is to enhance the model's accuracy and enable it to utilize land-based, marine-based, or integrated land-sea models in practical simulation computations.

297

298

299

300

301

302

303

304

305

306

307

Regarding the second research question—whether this framework can effectively reflect the patterns of continuous land-sea spatial mobility—two key technical considerations arise.

Unified Model Precision: The model must process both land and marine movements within the same precision framework to ensure continuity in the analysis results. However, we observed that the cost surface for maritime movement exhibits significantly less variation than its terrestrial counterpart, a characteristic that may be influenced by the specific study area. Consequently, the simulated movement paths tend to favor maritime routes (Figure 4a) or coastal pathways (Figure 7a). Is this trend consistent when examining specific population diffusion cases? Archaeologists have noted that Austronesian populations carried agricultural technologies during their maritime expansions (Bellwood 1979; Higham 2019; Diamond and Bellwood 2003). Additionally, geneticists have analyzed the relationships between various flora and fauna, such as poultry and fruit trees,

308 on remote islands and those along the southeastern coasts of Asia (Vilar et al. 2008; McColl et al.
309 2018). Therefore, from a macrogeographic spatial analysis perspective, the ocean can be
310 considered an *Express Train*, as Bellwood suggested (Bellwood 1979), rather than a barrier.
311 However, enriching maritime data to capture more complex scenarios remains a challenge.

312 *Cultural Considerations:* Building on the previous point, the choice between maritime and
313 terrestrial diffusion may be linked to the cultural attributes of the Austronesian populations. These
314 cultural factors are embedded in linguistic vocabularies. For instance, cognate analysis reveals
315 that although the Austronesian language families and Sino-Tibetan language families are
316 structurally different, they share a certain level of underlying logical similarity (Deng Xiaohua &
317 Wang Shiyuan 2003; Blust 2013; Guo Jianxin, Deng Xiaohua, & Wang Chuanchao 2023).
318 Additionally, artifacts under archaeological analysis suggest the presence of trade or exchange
319 phenomena among the Austronesian populations (Gibbons 2016). Consequently, exploring the
320 patterns of continuous spatial mobility necessitates the inclusion of non-spatial factors. Addressing
321 these cultural dimensions is necessary for land and sea be genuinely integrated into a unified
322 analytical framework.

323 Regarding the final research question, whether this framework can corroborate evidence of the
324 Austronesians discovered in archaeology, linguistics, and genetics, and possess the potential for
325 cultural interpretation. Undoubtedly, this unequivocally is the the ultimate objective of this
326 exploratory framework.

327 Firstly, the Mediterranean digital route network, for esample ORBIS project
328 (<https://orbis.stanford.edu/>) demonstrates the powerful potential of modeling maritime mobility
329 (Arcenas 2015). However, modeling movement in the Pacific presents distinct challenges. The
330 Pacific Ocean is vastly more expansive than the Mediterranean, and critically, it lacks the rich
331 digital historical records that underpin a more system project in the future. Therefore, our
332 simulation for the prehistoric Pacific necessitates a carefully considered selection and organization
333 of environmental parameters. Monte Carlo simulations are well-suited for assessing perception
334 and action probabilities for journeys with unknown start and end points (Fisher et al. 1997). This
335 approach, integrating random points with least-cost analysis, can effectively identify regions of high
336 accessibility within a study area (Gustas and Supernant 2017a; 2019).

337 Secondly, at present, the Austronesian language family remains a pivotal subject in studying
338 early human origins and diffusion (Diamond and Bellwood 2003; Djami and Suroto 2023; Thao et
339 al. 2024). Current research lacks a digital platform and model framework that encompasses multi-
340 source data, particularly because traversing both land and sea involves different mediums with
341 complex and integrative spatial characteristics. Presently, the scope of this exploratory framework
342 model is applied in the southeastern coasts of Asia. Ideally, future developments would integrate
343 empirical materials related to the Austronesians dispersed throughout the Pacific into this system,
344 further evolving it into a knowledge-based pathfinding system (Wiener, Büchner, and Hölischer
345 2009). The digital efforts based on the *Exploratory Framework Land-Sea Movement Model* are
346 foundational for reconstructing the maritime history of the Austronesians, thereby facilitating a
347 deeper understanding of their maritime spatial dynamics and cultural exchanges.

348 In summary, the innovation of this exploratory framework lies in its attempt to consider
349 continuous land-sea spatial movement through digital modeling, making it applicable to cases like
350 the Austronesians that involve both continental and marine diffusion. This approach effectively
351 reflects the relationship between spatial dynamics and human movement. Currently, the
352 framework is limited as a preliminary model and requires the incorporation of additional parameters
353 to enhance accuracy. This refinement process will be applied and validated in the researchers'
354 ongoing studies of the Austronesians' diffusion.

355 **Acknowledgements**

356 We are grateful to the open source website for providing us with maritime environmental data
357 such as wind and waves, which are helpful for this study. The specific website is as follows:

- 358 1. <http://www.gscloud.cn>, Geospatial Data Cloud platform, administered by the Chinese
359 Academy of Sciences.
360 2. <http://apdrc.soest.hawaii.edu/las86>, Asia-Pacific Data Research Center, by the National
361 Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA).

362 Funding

363 Supported by: the Research Initiative Fund for Newly Introduced Talents of Harbin Institute of
364 Technology, Shenzhen (#ZX20230488); the Special Fund for Humanities and Social Sciences
365 Development in Harbin Institute of Technology (Shenzhen): Landscape archaeology analysis on
366 the power control network of Liangzhu Heritage Sites, (# 2021-8).

367 Conflict of interest disclosure

368 The authors declare that they comply with the PCI rule of having no financial conflicts of interest
369 in relation to the content of the article.

370 Data, scripts, code, and supplementary information availability

371 Data are available online: <https://zenodo.org/records/14997617>; Luo Hongpeng, 2025

372 References

- 373 Alberti, Gianmarco. 2018. 'TRANSIT: A GIS Toolbox for Estimating the Duration of Ancient Sail-
374 Powered Navigation'. *Cartography and Geographic Information Science* 45 (6): 510–28.
375 <https://doi.org/10.1080/15230406.2017.1403376>.
- 376 Arcenas, Scott. 2015. 'ORBIS and the Sea: A Model for Maritime Transportation under the Roman
377 Empire'.
- 378 Bellwood, Peter. 1979. *Man's Conquest of the Pacific: The Prehistory of Southeast Asia and Oceania*.
379 Oxford University Press.
- 380 ———. 2007. *Prehistory of the Indo-Malaysian Archipelago*. Canberra: ANU Press.
- 381 ———. 2017. *First Islanders: Prehistory and Human Migration in Island Southeast Asia*. Edited by
382 Colin Groves, Debbie Argue, Hirofumi Matsumura, Marc Oxenham, Truman Simanjuntak,
383 Mariko Yamagata, Murray Cox, et al. Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119251583>.
- 384 ———. 2024. 'Archaeogenetics: Tracing Ancient Migrations from the Yellow River'. *Current Biology*
385 34 (1): R18–20. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2023.11.024>.
- 386 Bellwood, Peter, James J. Fox, D. T. Tryon, and Australian National University, eds. 1995. *The*
387 *Austronesians: Historical and Comparative Perspectives*. Canberra: Dept. of Anthropology as
388 part of the Comparative Austronesian Project, Research School of Pacific and Asian Studies,
389 Australian National University.
- 390 Bilotti, Giacomo, Michael Kempf, and Jose Miguel Morillo Leon. 2024. 'Modelling Land and Water
391 Based Movement Corridors in the Western Mediterranean: A Least Cost Path Analysis from
392 Chalcolithic and Early Bronze Age Ivory Records'. *Archaeological and Anthropological*
393 *Sciences* 16 (8): 122. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12520-024-02029-x>.
- 394 Blust, Robert. 2013. *The Austronesian Languages*. Revised Edition. Pacific Linguistics 602. Canberra:
395 Australian National University.
- 396 Bradshaw, Corey J. A., Sean Ulm, Alan N. Williams, Michael I. Bird, Richard G. Roberts, Zenobia
397 Jacobs, Fiona Laviano, et al. 2019. 'Minimum Founding Populations for the First Peopling of
398 Sahul'. *Nature Ecology & Evolution* 3 (7): 1057–63. [https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-019-0902-](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-019-0902-6)
399 6.
- 400 Di Piazza, Anne. 2014. 'An Isochrone Map of the Prehistoric Seascape around S Amoa'. *Geographical*
401 *Research* 52 (1): 74–84. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1745-5871.12037>.
- 402 Diamond, Jared, and Peter Bellwood. 2003. 'Farmers and Their Languages: The First Expansions'.
403 *Science* 300 (5619): 597–603. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1078208>.

- 404 Dickson, Thomas, Helen Farr, David Sear, and James I R Blake. 2019. 'Uncertainty in Marine Weather
405 Routing'. *Applied Ocean Research* 88 (July):138–46.
406 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.apor.2019.04.008>.
- 407 Djami, Erlin Novita Idje, and Hari Suroto. 2023. 'Distribution of Austronesian Languages and
408 Archaeology in Western New Guinea, Indonesia'. *L'Anthropologie* 127 (3): 103153.
409 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anthro.2023.103153>.
- 410 ESRI. 2025a. 'Adjust the Encountered Distance Using a Cost Surface'. 2025.
411 [https://pro.arcgis.com/en/pro-app/latest/tool-reference/spatial-analyst/adjust-the-encountered-](https://pro.arcgis.com/en/pro-app/latest/tool-reference/spatial-analyst/adjust-the-encountered-distance-using-a-cost-surface.htm)
412 [distance-using-a-cost-surface.htm](https://pro.arcgis.com/en/pro-app/latest/tool-reference/spatial-analyst/adjust-the-encountered-distance-using-a-cost-surface.htm).
- 413 ———. 2025b. 'Adjust the Encountered Distance Using a Horizontal Factor'. 2025.
414 [https://pro.arcgis.com/en/pro-app/latest/tool-reference/spatial-analyst/adjust-the-encountered-](https://pro.arcgis.com/en/pro-app/latest/tool-reference/spatial-analyst/adjust-the-encountered-distance-using-a-horizontal-factor.htm)
415 [distance-using-a-horizontal-factor.htm](https://pro.arcgis.com/en/pro-app/latest/tool-reference/spatial-analyst/adjust-the-encountered-distance-using-a-horizontal-factor.htm).
- 416 ———. 2025c. 'Adjust the Encountered Distance Using a Vertical Factor'. 2025.
417 [https://pro.arcgis.com/en/pro-app/latest/tool-reference/spatial-analyst/adjust-the-encountered-](https://pro.arcgis.com/en/pro-app/latest/tool-reference/spatial-analyst/adjust-the-encountered-distance-using-a-vertical-factor.htm)
418 [distance-using-a-vertical-factor.htm](https://pro.arcgis.com/en/pro-app/latest/tool-reference/spatial-analyst/adjust-the-encountered-distance-using-a-vertical-factor.htm).
- 419 ———. 2025d. 'Connect Locations with Corridors'. 2025. [https://pro.arcgis.com/en/pro-](https://pro.arcgis.com/en/pro-app/latest/tool-reference/spatial-analyst/connect-locations-with-corridors.htm)
420 [app/latest/tool-reference/spatial-analyst/connect-locations-with-corridors.htm](https://pro.arcgis.com/en/pro-app/latest/tool-reference/spatial-analyst/connect-locations-with-corridors.htm).
- 421 ———. 2025e. 'Distance Accumulation'. 2025. [https://pro.arcgis.com/en/pro-app/latest/tool-](https://pro.arcgis.com/en/pro-app/latest/tool-reference/spatial-analyst/distance-accumulation.htm)
422 [reference/spatial-analyst/distance-accumulation.htm](https://pro.arcgis.com/en/pro-app/latest/tool-reference/spatial-analyst/distance-accumulation.htm).
- 423 ———. 2025f. 'How Distance Accumulation Works'. 2025. [https://pro.arcgis.com/en/pro-](https://pro.arcgis.com/en/pro-app/latest/tool-reference/spatial-analyst/how-distance-accumulation-works.htm)
424 [app/latest/tool-reference/spatial-analyst/how-distance-accumulation-works.htm](https://pro.arcgis.com/en/pro-app/latest/tool-reference/spatial-analyst/how-distance-accumulation-works.htm).
- 425 ———. 2025g. 'Least Cost Corridor'. 2025. [https://pro.arcgis.com/en/pro-app/latest/tool-](https://pro.arcgis.com/en/pro-app/latest/tool-reference/spatial-analyst/least-cost-corridor.htm)
426 [reference/spatial-analyst/least-cost-corridor.htm](https://pro.arcgis.com/en/pro-app/latest/tool-reference/spatial-analyst/least-cost-corridor.htm).
- 427 ———. 2025h. 'Optimal Path As Line'. 2025. [https://pro.arcgis.com/en/pro-app/latest/tool-](https://pro.arcgis.com/en/pro-app/latest/tool-reference/spatial-analyst/optimal-path-as-line.htm)
428 [reference/spatial-analyst/optimal-path-as-line.htm](https://pro.arcgis.com/en/pro-app/latest/tool-reference/spatial-analyst/optimal-path-as-line.htm).
- 429 Ferentinos, George, Maria Gkioni, Maria Geraga, and George Papatheodorou. 2012. 'Early Seafaring
430 Activity in the Southern Ionian Islands, Mediterranean Sea'. *Journal of Archaeological Science*
431 39 (7): 2167–76. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2012.01.032>.
- 432 Fisher, Peter, Chris Farrelly, Adrian Maddocks, and Clive Ruggles. 1997. 'Spatial Analysis of Visible
433 Areas from the Bronze Age Cairns of Mull'. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 24 (7): 581–
434 92. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jasc.1996.0142>.
- 435 Gal, D., H. Saaroni, and D. Cvikel. 2023. 'Windward Sailing in Antiquity: The Elephant in the Room'.
436 *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology* 52 (1): 179–94.
437 <https://doi.org/10.1080/10572414.2023.2186688>.
- 438 Gatty, Harold. 1999. *Finding Your Way without Map or Compass*. Mineola, N.Y: Dover Publications.
- 439 Gauthier, Nicolas. 2019. 'Trade, Migration, and the Dynamics of Spatial Interaction'. Preprint.
440 SocArXiv. <https://doi.org/10.31235/osf.io/trbf8>.
- 441 Gheorghide, Paula, and Christine Spencer. 2024. 'Modelling the Cost of the Wind: A Preliminary
442 Reassessment of Networks of Mobility in the Late Bronze Age Mediterranean'. *Journal of*
443 *Computer Applications in Archaeology* 7 (1): 36–53. <https://doi.org/10.5334/jcaa.119>.
- 444 Gibbons, Ann. 2016. 'First Polynesians Launched from East Asia to Settle Pacific'. *Science* 354 (6308):
445 24–25. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.354.6308.24>.
- 446 Gillings, Mark, Piraye Hacigüzeller, and G. R. Lock, eds. 2020. *Archaeological Spatial Analysis: A*
447 *Methodological Guide*. New York: Routledge.
- 448 Gooley, Tristan. 2017. *How to Read Nature: Awaken Your Senses to the Outdoors You've Never*
449 *Noticed: Taste Direction, Smell Time, Hear the Weather, and More*. New York: Experiment.
- 450 Gustas, Robert, and Kisha Supernant. 2017a. 'Least Cost Path Analysis of Early Maritime Movement
451 on the Pacific Northwest Coast'. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 78 (February):40–56.
452 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2016.11.006>.
- 453 ———. 2017b. 'Least Cost Path Analysis of Early Maritime Movement on the Pacific Northwest
454 Coast'. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 78 (February):40–56.
455 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2016.11.006>.
- 456 ———. 2019. 'Coastal Migration into the Americas and Least Cost Path Analysis'. *Journal of*
457 *Anthropological Archaeology* 54 (June):192–206. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaa.2019.04.006>.

- 458 Harpster, Matthew, and Henry Chapman. 2019. 'Using Polygons to Model Maritime Movement in
459 Antiquity'. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 111 (November):104997.
460 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2019.104997>.
- 461 He, Jie. 2008. 'GIS-Based Cultural Route Heritage Authenticity Analysis and Conservation Support in
462 Cost-Surface and Visibility Study Approaches'. The Chinese University of Hong Kong (Hong
463 Kong).
- 464 Hengl, Tomislav. 2006. 'Finding the Right Pixel Size'. *Computers & Geosciences* 32 (9): 1283–98.
465 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cageo.2005.11.008>.
- 466 Higham, Charles F. W. 2019. 'A Maritime Route Brought First Farmers to Mainland Southeast Asia'.
467 In *Prehistoric Maritime Cultures and Seafaring in East Asia*, edited by Chunming Wu and
468 Barry Vladimir Rolett, 1:41–52. The Archaeology of Asia-Pacific Navigation. Singapore:
469 Springer Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-32-9256-7_2.
- 470 Ihara, Yasuo, Kazunobu Ikeya, Atsushi Nobayashi, and Yosuke Kaifu. 2020. 'A Demographic Test of
471 Accidental versus Intentional Island Colonization by Pleistocene Humans'. *Journal of Human
472 Evolution* 145 (August):102839. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2020.102839>.
- 473 Indruszewski, George, and C. Michael Barton. 2008. 'Cost Surface DEM Modelling of Viking Age
474 Seafaring in the Baltic Sea'. In *Beyond Illustration: 2D and 3D Digital Technologies as Tools
475 for Discovery in Archaeology*, 56–64. International Series.
- 476 Leidwanger, Justin. 2013. 'Modeling Distance with Time in Ancient Mediterranean Seafaring: A GIS
477 Application for the Interpretation of Maritime Connectivity'. *Journal of Archaeological
478 Science* 40 (8): 3302–8. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2013.03.016>.
- 479 Leusen, Pieter Martijn van. 2002. *Pattern to Process: Methodological Investigations into the Formation
480 and Interpretation of Spatial Patterns in Archaeological Landscapes*. University of Groningen.
- 481 Lewis, David. 1964. 'Ara Moana: Stars of the Sea Road'. *Journal of Navigation* 17 (3): 278–88.
482 <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0373463300037498>.
- 483 ———. 1966. 'Stars of the Sea Road'. *The Journal of the Polynesian Society* 75 (1): 84–94.
- 484 ———. 1972. *We, the Navigators: The Ancient Art of Landfinding in the Pacific*. First Edition.
485 Australian National University Press.
- 486 ———. 1974. 'Wind, Wave, Star, and Bird'. *National Geographic*.
- 487 Liu, Yan, Lanjie Deng, Jin He, Xiaoshuang Zhao, Huimin Wang, Dan Feng, Jing Chen, Maotian Li,
488 and Qianli Sun. 2021. 'Holocene Geomorphological Evolution and the Neolithic Occupation
489 in South Hangzhou Bay, China'. *Geomorphology* 389 (September):107827.
490 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2021.107827>.
- 491 Llobera, Marcos. 2000. 'Understanding Movement: A Pilot Model towards the Sociology of
492 Movement'. In *Understanding Movement: A Pilot Model towards the Sociology of Movement*,
493 65–84. Amsterdam: IOS Press.
- 494 McColl, Hugh, Fernando Racimo, Lasse Vinner, Fabrice Demeter, Takashi Gakuhari, J. Víctor Moreno-
495 Mayar, George Van Driem, et al. 2018. 'The Prehistoric Peopling of Southeast Asia'. *Science*
496 361 (6397): 88–92. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aat3628>.
- 497 McLean, Andrew, and Xavier Rubio-Campillo. 2022. 'Beyond Least Cost Paths: Circuit Theory,
498 Maritime Mobility and Patterns of Urbanism in the Roman Adriatic'. *Journal of Archaeological
499 Science* 138 (February):105534. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2021.105534>.
- 500 Mehrer, Mark. 2005. *GIS and Archaeological Site Location Modeling*. Milton: Taylor & Francis Group.
- 501 Moutsiou, Theodora, and Athos Agapiou. 2019. 'Least Cost Pathway Analysis of Obsidian Circulation
502 in Early Holocene–Early Middle Holocene Cyprus'. *Journal of Archaeological Science:
503 Reports* 26 (August):101881. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jasrep.2019.101881>.
- 504 Perttola, Wesa. 2022. 'Digital Navigator on the Seas of the Selden Map of China: Sequential Least-
505 Cost Path Analysis Using Dynamic Wind Data'. *Journal of Archaeological Method and Theory*
506 29 (2): 688–721. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10816-021-09534-6>.
- 507 Puleston, Cedric, and Bruce Winterhalder. 2019. 'Demography, Environment, and Human Behavior'.
508 In *Handbook of Evolutionary Research in Archaeology*, edited by Anna Marie Prentiss, 311–
509 35. Cham: Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-11117-5_16.
- 510 Ruxton, Graeme D., and David M. Wilkinson. 2012. 'Population Trajectories for Accidental versus
511 Planned Colonisation of Islands'. *Journal of Human Evolution* 63 (3): 507–11.
512 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhevol.2012.05.013>.

- 513 Safadi, Crystal. 2016. 'Wind and Wave Modelling for the Evaluation of the Maritime Accessibility and
514 Protection Afforded by Ancient Harbours'. *Journal of Archaeological Science: Reports* 5
515 (February):348–60. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jasrep.2015.12.004>.
- 516 Safadi, Crystal, and Fraser Sturt. 2019. 'The Warped Sea of Sailing: Maritime Topographies of Space
517 and Time for the Bronze Age Eastern Mediterranean'. *Journal of Archaeological Science* 103
518 (March):1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jas.2019.01.001>.
- 519 Shennan, Stephen, and Rebecca Sear. 2021. 'Archaeology, Demography and Life History Theory
520 Together Can Help Us Explain Past and Present Population Patterns'. *Philosophical
521 Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences* 376 (1816): 20190711.
522 <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2019.0711>.
- 523 Thao, Dinh Huong, Tran Huu Dinh, Shigeki Mitsunaga, La Duc Duy, Nguyen Thanh Phuong, Nguyen
524 Phuong Anh, Nguyen Tho Anh, et al. 2024. 'Investigating Demic versus Cultural Diffusion and
525 Sex Bias in the Spread of Austronesian Languages in Vietnam'. Edited by Christian Reepmeyer.
526 *PLOS ONE* 19 (6): e0304964. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0304964>.
- 527 Trapero Fernández, Pedro, and Enrique Aragón. 2022. 'Modelling Cabotage. Coastal Navigation in the
528 Western Mediterranean Sea during the Early Iron Age'. *Journal of Archaeological Science:
529 Reports* 41 (February):103270. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jasrep.2021.103270>.
- 530 Tryon, D. T., and D. T. Tryon, eds. 2011. *Comparative Austronesian Dictionary: An Introduction to
531 Austronesian Studies*. Originally published 1994. Trends in Linguistics. Documentation 10.
532 Berlin ;New York: De Gruyter. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110884012>.
- 533 Verhagen, Philip, Laure Nuninger, and Mark R. Groenhuijzen. 2019. 'Modelling of Pathways and
534 Movement Networks in Archaeology: An Overview of Current Approaches'. In *Finding the
535 Limits of the Limes*, edited by Philip Verhagen, Jamie Joyce, and Mark R. Groenhuijzen, 217–
536 49. Computational Social Sciences. Cham: Springer International Publishing.
537 https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-04576-0_11.
- 538 Vilar, Miguel G., Akira Kaneko, Francis W. Hombhanje, Takahiro Tsukahara, Ilomo Hwaihwanje, and
539 J. Koji Lum. 2008. 'Reconstructing the Origin of the Lapita Cultural Complex: mtDNA
540 Analyses of East Sepik Province, PNG'. *Journal of Human Genetics* 53 (8): 698–708.
541 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10038-008-0301-3>.
- 542 Wei, Lan-Hai, Shi Yan, Yik-Ying Teo, Yun-Zhi Huang, Ling-Xiang Wang, Ge Yu, Woei-Yuh Saw, et
543 al. 2017. 'Phylogeography of Y-Chromosome Haplogroup O3a2b2-N6 Reveals Patrilineal
544 Traces of Austronesian Populations on the Eastern Coastal Regions of Asia'. Edited by
545 Gyaneshwer Chaubey. *PLOS ONE* 12 (4): e0175080.
546 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0175080>.
- 547 Wheatley, David, and Mark Gillings. 2002. *Spatial Technology and Archaeology: The Archaeological
548 Applications of GIS*. London, New York: Taylor & Francis.
- 549 Whitewright, Julian. 2011. 'The Potential Performance of Ancient Mediterranean Sailing Rigs: THE
550 POTENTIAL PERFORMANCE OF ANCIENT MEDITERRANEAN SAILING RIGS'.
551 *International Journal of Nautical Archaeology* 40 (1): 2–17. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1095-9270.2010.00276.x>.
- 552
- 553 Wiener, Jan M., Simon J. Büchner, and Christoph Hölscher. 2009. 'Taxonomy of Human Wayfinding
554 Tasks: A Knowledge-Based Approach'. *Spatial Cognition & Computation* 9 (2): 152–65.
555 <https://doi.org/10.1080/13875860902906496>.
- 556 Yang, Melinda A., Xuechun Fan, Bo Sun, Chungyu Chen, Jianfeng Lang, Ying-Chin Ko, Cheng-hwa
557 Tsang, et al. 2020. 'Ancient DNA Indicates Human Population Shifts and Admixture in
558 Northern and Southern China'. *Science* 369 (6501): 282–88.
559 <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aba0909>.
- 560 邓晓华 and 王士元. 2003. '藏缅语族语言的数理分类及其分析'. 民族语文, no. 4, 8–18.
- 561 ———. 2007. '壮侗语族语言的数理分类及其时间深度'. 中国语文, no. 6, 536-548+576.
- 562 郭健新, 邓晓华, and 王传超. 2023. '南岛语族起源与扩散的考古学和古基因组学观察'. 台湾研究
563 集刊, no. 5, 31–47. <https://doi.org/10.14157/j.cnki.twrq.2023.05.009>.